

**LEXICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPUTER TERMS IN ENGLISH,
UZBEK AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES**

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Abstract

The article is devoted to expose, analyse and study of the structural and semantic characteristics of computer terms in English. The peculiarities of the wordformation process and the functioning of English computer terms are analysed.

Keywords: terminology, linguistic phenomenon, terminology, jargon, slang, internet, computer, technology, language, professional.

The "information revolution" was a phenomena brought about by the tremendous advancements in science and technology toward the end of the 20th century. The number of new terminology for new fields of knowledge has increased dramatically due to the dynamic expansion of research and technology. When it comes to advances, the information and communication technology field is among the most sophisticated. Since the majority of inventions in this subject are produced in the US, it seems sense that their nominations are made in English. On the other hand, computer terminology has become more international due to the worldwide nature of computerization. Numerous computers are utilized in daily life in addition to the workplace. As a result, a large number of computer phrases have moved from the domain of specialized language to that of ordinary language. As a result, computer slang is formed. The acquisition of computer vocabulary occurs simultaneously alongside the use of information and communication innovations. The fact that computer language is dynamic lends significance to this subject. Rather, it is in a state of continuous and dynamic evolution, changing and expanding its vocabulary with new words. Computer-related Americanisms are always adding richness to British English, however several computer phrases are still missing from specialized dictionaries. Despite the fact that a large body of academic literature has been written about computer vocabulary and its translation (written by people like V. Akulenko, F. Baranov, I. Bolshakov, D. Crystal, N. Gritsak, V. Karaban, O. Medvid, Y. Pylypovych, R. Pronin, A. Savina, R. Syndega, V. Tabakanova, A. Fedorov, M. Chernyshov, and others), term differentiation structural (written by people like D. Barannik, R. Dubuc, K. Gaivenis, T. Kiyak, Z. Kudelko, S. Pavel, E. Yenikeva, M. Kochergan, etc.), word-

formation techniques, and term systems (written by people like N. Begzholova, L. Verba, N. Vinogradova, M. [1:56]

There is a clear correlation between the rate of development of a certain scientific and technological subject and the formation and evolution of specialized words. It is evident that an area that is well developed includes a lot of specialized words. As to Kocherhan, linguistic and extralinguistic variables can bring about alterations in a terminological system. Linguistic influences include shifts in the language's lexicon associated with a drive toward unification, the systematics of linguistic methods, and variations in nominations with distinct purposes and tasks including emotive and stylistic expression.

Extralinguistic influences include shifts in the world brought about by the quick advancement of science and technology as well as advances in the social and cultural domains and human daily existence. Kizil specifically mentions that extralinguistic factors like informatization, computerization of English-speaking societies and the global community at large, the development and spread of the internet sphere and cyberspace, globalization processes, the spread of English, the importance of linguistic coding of concepts, and the realities of computer-mediated realities by its means are some of the extralinguistic factors that have an impact on the evolution of the computer term system. As a result, language is a reflection of the world around it. Only as a part of a term system can terms exist. [2:77]

Given that it was formed and developed at a time of intense innovation in the field of information technology at the end of the 20th century, this term system is among the youngest terminology used in the field of information technology that have a clear, established definition are known as computer terminology. The fact that these terminology properly convey the ideas, procedures, and names of items that are unique to information technology is a noteworthy characteristic of them. "Computer language," according to Jaleniauskiene and Čičelytė, is a unique language created in the area and technologically associated with the manufacture of personal computers and their software.[3:98]

CONCLUSION

Computer terms can also be defined as lexical units that actualize substantial information as well as cognitive-figurative experiences related to informatics, computer technology, and internet communication. These units are distinguished by

the structural-semantic interdependence of their constituent parts. Exploring words may be done in two primary ways: normative and descriptive. According to the normative method, terms are studied as words (or phrases) that belong to a certain field of application, designating a particular notion that has to be defined. Thus, a word differs from common lexis in terms of its structural and semantic properties. The descriptive method examines terms as any lexical unit with a distinct purpose. The terms that make up the computer term system fall into the following categories:

1. Terms that are connected with frequent terms. These terminologies originate from the regular usage of words that take on IT-specific connotations. The term in this instance is a commonly used word (e.g., assembler, backdoor, cable, click, bus, bug), card, chat, break, drive, default, button, edit, copy, disable, page, account, alias, application, cookies.
2. General terms that have multiple meanings in different branches of science and technology, in addition to the computer term system (e.g., "driver," which refers to the program in a computer context that controls information input and output but has dozens of other meanings in other branches of science and technology).
3. Terms unique to computers alone. Terms like cyberspace, hypertext, subnet, ewallet, hyperlink, cyberspace, microblog, and cybercommuter are a few examples. Other terms include cybernetics, hardware, software, cyberprofilers, technomedia, ecabinet, e-money, webfare, cybercrook, cybernerd, and e-surfer. Under these circumstances, the term's semantics and meaning coincide since the word expresses a single, unique notion; in other words, the term's semantics and meaning are compatible.
4. Terminologies have several meanings in the field of computers. The word "server," for instance, refers to both an internet-accessible computer and an application that offers access to the internet; the verb "display" implies

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